

GRADUATE TRACER STUDY OF MASTER OF ARTS IN EDUCATION MAJOR IN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION BATSTATE-U

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ABSTRACT

This tracer study primarily determined the employability and performance of the of CTE MAEd-EM graduates in the inclusive AY 2015-2016- AY 2018-2019 with the end view of proposing a curriculum enhancement plan in order to produce globally competitive graduates. It also determined the respondents' job placement profile, extent of the program's contribution to their personal and professional growth and their work performance. The descriptive method of research was applied in the study using questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument. The participants of the study were the MAEd-EM graduates of Batangas State University. Results revealed that majority of the graduates from MAEd-EM are in the age bracket of 31-40, female, married, BEED graduates, LET passers, permanently employed in public institution, took up their advance study for professional development, work as Master Teachers III and Teacher I, have been employed for 6-10 years, and PAFTE members. They assessed that master's program contributed to their personal and professional growth to a very great extent. The employers strongly agreed that they have shown critical thinking skills and work ethics in performing their job. It was recommended that the prepared curriculum enhancement activities may be used for the different courses to attain higher level of competencies of graduates.

Keywords: tracer study, MAED EM, curriculum enhancement plan, employability and performance